

Computable Continuous Functions, in the design of BEAMOS based auto navigation.

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Abstract:

The design paradigm of analog circuits with computable continuous functions in MFA, applied to two port networks, as DPA is introduced for multi sensor and Nv and Nu neuron designs in universal two port network topologies.

The paradigm is illustrated with abcde, a robot made from off the shelf components, such as Lego Motors.

Keywords:

MAFA I, MFA II, BEAMOS, Computable Continuous Functions , DPA

What:

MFA I and II designs with continuous computable functions define CTM designs implemented with simple circuits, with transfer resistance properties. In this paper we illustrate two port networks with computable continuous functions, as an implementation of a BEAMOS, with the example of DPA written as functions and implemented in BEAM or MFA I hardware.

How:

We define DPA as a set of functions, defined in continuous computable functions defined in the framework of Lie Computability in lattice theory embeddings and the existence of maps to the implementation in transfer resistance , in two port networks of BEAM circuits. ¹Auto Navigation is defined in a simple functional framework, with simple sensor 1D waveforms and simple actions in Nu and Nv neurons and action elements. We illustrate with "Simply" the bathtub BEAM turtle, automated with a proximity sensor.

Why:

BEAMOS in robotics as popularized by Wow Wee Toys, is robotic sculpture, and also art therapy implemented anywhere, in this paper simple emergence in continuous function theory implements emergent A.I in simple BEAM based toys.

Introduction.

Tensor Decompositions ²are often used to describe network topologies, while most forms of TMs and CTMs are defined by Tensor

Decompositions, we mathematically formulate the limits of tensor definitions of learning and MFA II networks using a concept of Z-Completeness in Lie Computability³ defined in

the E8 Universe, in representation theoretical models of the Universe.

In this paper on CTMs defined in a framework of DPA to create BEAM circuits, we define gestalts of symmetry, computability as time defined stability and closed form expressions of behaviour and closure, in polynomial time with analogous asymptotics.

Problem Definition.

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DPA is in the MFA design paradigm, written in mathematical closed form, as continuous computable functions, implemented in computability by CTMs.⁴ A CTM can be created in a network topology of generalized two port networks to create a network topology of N_v and N_u neurons.

We define a formal methodology for a map between the circuit topology and the DPA as $[F,S,A]$ as $([S],[N_v],[N_u],[A])$

In the example of auto navigation, we define a simple function of reversal of direction on a predicate of proximity on sensor s .

$f(s) = N_v_polarity_reverser(A)$ for an action two port element A .

Defined as a simple computable continuous function as a bistable element of states $+$ and $-$, with a map from s as a predicate in a logistic function, $l(s) \rightarrow S$, $f(S) = N_v_bistable+- (A)$

More complicated DPA functions like the bouncing ball simulation, particle simulation and filter with an ergodic and a goal directed behaviour can be defined similar to active filter theory.^{5,6}

</original-contribution>

Discussion.

Computable Continuous Function theory is defined in automation with the example of a DPA system, for the emergence of auto navigation by simple obstacle avoidance functions, to bouncing ball, diffusion, ergodic and exploratory with goal direction particle filters, several 'data structure' for CTMs are defined, such as trees and graphs.

Computability is easily defined in the context of Lie Computability, in the gestalt⁷ of symmetry and closure, proving polynomial time convergence or stability theorems in closed form descriptions for time dependent behaviours.

In the case of the function defined earlier, namely a bistable state machine pattern, closure and symmetry are easily defined on two states^{8,9} and a mapping from one to any of the two states for each state, and the finite time needed for transitions converging sensors and actions in transitions, with symmetries on the behaviours in MFA I defined as the computability definitions in the BEAMOS.¹⁰

Future Work.

In future work we define an active filter and ergodicity based DPA,¹¹ with a variety of definitions for path or trajectory, a tensor approach, a tree approach (without cycles) and a graph approach (with cycles) with filters for a particle simulation, in an approximation of the turtle as a particle.

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